

SURVEY OF AN ENERGY-EFFICIENT STRESS MONITORING SYSTEM USING PHYSIOLOGICAL DATA

¹Murali. D, ²Mr.M.S.Muhammadu Sathik Raja. M.E.,M.B.A,

¹ Student , ²HOD,

^{1,2} Department of Medical Electronics,

^{1,2} Sengunthar College of Engineering, Tiruchengode,

dmurali4all@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

Anxiety is your body's natural response to stress. People with anxiety disorders frequently have intense, excessive and persistent worry and fear about everyday situations. As we know stress is the main cause of long-term health disorder, Stress management is so necessary to maintain an individual's stress levels keep down and able to reduce health risks.

In this article, we are finding out some measures and methods through which we employ low-cost wearable sensors collection of data and machine learning algorithms to predict an individual's stress level so as to manage his stress level. Researchers have found out that stress levels can also be detected using physiological tests such as pulse rate, heart rate amplitude and skin infections or skin diseases.

This research paper' main aim is to offer a necessary analysis of various kinds of stress detection and to find out different methods to overcome it as well as a reliable checklist for more effective stress detection.

Keywords—Anxiety detection, feature extraction, physiological measures, wearable sensors, machine learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traumatic stress is very normal in today's fast-paced society. Stress may be induced by circumstances or activities that place strain on a person's mind and body. Everyone's reaction to stress is unique, as is their ability to cope with difficult or demanding conditions. Some conditions can cause stress in one person while causing no stress in another. Furthermore, all stress is not harmful to health because it will make people more conscious of their surroundings, keep them warier of risks, and keep them focused on their target. A stressor is an occurrence that creates stress in a person. Many people experience stress as a result of the stressors mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1. Stressor type and its examples

Type of stressor	Description and Examples
Physical	Strain on a body Ex: Injury, illness, pain, travel, infection, excess alcohol

Psychological	Anything interpreted as threatening or challenging for mind Ex: Money problem, exams, loss of employment, excessive worrying
Environmental	Associated with surrounding Ex: Noise, crowd, air

The American Psychological Association (APA) classifies stress into three types: acute stress, episodic acute stress, and chronic stress. Acute stress is the least harmful form of stress as compared to the other two. It can be beneficial at times because it enables the body in dealing with the situation. When a person experiences acute stress on a regular basis, he or she is suffering from episodic acute stress. Chronic stress is the most dangerous form of stress, and if left unchecked for an extended period of time, it will affect a person's physical and mental health. Chronic stress exerts long-term pressure on the body and mind, resulting in a variety of symptoms and an increased chance of contracting such diseases. People who are at high risk of being depressed should be constantly watched to spot any stress symptoms in order to prevent health complications. Wearable devices make it possible to track stress and warn people of their stress levels, which can be helpful in reducing stress until it causes severe health issues. Since physical and mental wellbeing are inextricably linked, tracking and assessing physiological and

physical changes may be used to identify human stress levels.

Functional and biochemical tests of the body may be used to track stress. Pulse rhythm, skin temperature, humidity, blood pressure, and respiration rate are examples of physical indicators, while physiological data include heart rate variation, heart rate variability, and skin conductance. These can be assessed using wearable devices made of low-cost sensors, but machine learning algorithms can be used to classify and forecast an individual's stress level. Any previous approaches to automated stress recognition systems that used sensors and machine learning are explored in detail in this article. Physiological evidence was collected from people using stressor measures in these studies. Arithmetic equations, questionnaires, mental exercises, and working out in the gym are some typical stressor tests. There are several machine learning algorithms that are suitable for stress detection. The most popular are Support Vector Machines (SVM), Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbor, Decision Tree, and Random Forest. We summarize the numerous machine learning algorithms available in the literature that attempt to detect the state of stress in this study. The remaining part of the paper is separated into two sections. Section II describes several strategies for detecting and classifying stress levels. Section III concludes the article and discusses the findings of the literature review.

2. RELATED WORK

In this section, we summarized a report of some approaches of stress detection. These methods differ in the kinds of stress-related factors and procedures used. The initiatives in this

methods are physical measures, physiological signals, answering queries, mathematical test, videos, blogging, and other techniques, etc.

Table 2. Overview of stress detection using sensors studies in chronological orders, their details and best accuracy achieved

Studies	Stressors	Population (Subjects)	Sensors	Classifiers/Algorithms/Models	Best Accuracy Achieved
Jacqueline Wijsman et al. (2011) [1]	Questionnaire, Mathematical Tasks	30	EMG ECG Respiration Skin Conductance	Linear Bayes Normal Classifier Quadratic Bayes Normal Classifier K-Nearest Neighbor Classifier Fisher's Least Square Linear	80%
Jongyoon Choi et al.(2012) [2]	Some Tests, Breathing exercise	10	MG Respiration Heart Rate	Stress Prediction Model Logistic Regression Model	81%
Muhammad Zubair et al.(2015) [3]	Tracking	12	Skin Conductance	Logistic Regression Model	91.66%
Anthonette D. Cantara et al. (2016) [4]	Interviews	21	Heart Rate Galvanic Skin Response	Fuzzy Logic Algorithm	72%
Purnendu Shekhar Pandey(2017) [5]	Age, Working out in Gym	318	Pulse Sensor Heart Rate	Logistic Regression Model Support Vector Machine Classifier	68%
Rachmad Setiawan et al.(2019) [6]	Tense and calm conditions	15	Temperature Galvanic Skin Response Heart Rate	Fuzzy Logic Algorithm	80%
Jorge Rodriguez- Arce et al.(2020) [7]	STAI self-report Questionnaire	21	Heart Rate Skin Temperature Galvanic Skin Response Pulse oximeter Breath-rate sensor	Support Vector Machine Classifier K-Nearest Neighbor Classifier Random Forest Classifier Logistic Regression Model	95.98%

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Because of today's demanding and aggressive lifestyle, emotional fatigue is very normal in all age groups. Early identification of depression can be very helpful in taking more steps and it can impair both an individual's emotional and physical health. Some researchers gathered physiological data signals to quantify tension using self-made wearable devices (using low-cost sensors) in the methods discussed above, whereas others depend on

commercial devices. The physiological signal necessary for detecting stress level was obtained by subjecting them to one or more stressors. All of the built systems extracted features using different algorithms before employing machine learning algorithms to construct classification models. It has been discovered that features derived from heart rate, heart rate variability, and skin conductance are more efficient in predicting an individual's stress level, while the most powerful

classification algorithms are support vector machine, random forest, and K-Nearest Neighbor.

This demonstrates that physiological signals can be used to detect stress in a person using wearable sensors and machine learning algorithms that are both accurate and inexpensive. The study's drawback is that many participants used different features that were associated with each other, which increased computation time. In addition, some of them used expensive commercial instruments to capture physiological signals while low-cost sensors should have been used.

4. REFERENCES

- [1].Jacqueline Wijsman, Bernard Grundlehner, Hao Liu, Hermie Hermens and Julien Penders, “Towards Mental Stress Detection Using Wearable Physiological Sensors”, International Conference of the IEEE EMBS Boston, Massachusetts, USA, pp.8-11, 2011, DOI: 10.1109/IEMBS.2011.6090512.
- [2].Jongyoon Choi, Beena Ahmed, and Ricardo Gutierrez-Osuna, Development and Evaluation of an Ambulatory Stress Monitor Based on Wearable Sensors”, IEEE Transactions on Information Technology in Biomedicine, Vol. 16, No. 2, pp.279-286, 2012, DOI 10.1109/TITB.2011.2169804.
- [3].Muhammad Zubair, Changwoo Yoon, Hyunyoung Kim, Jisu Kim and Jinsul Kim, “Smart Wearable Band for Stress Detection”, International Conference on IT Convergence and Security (ICITCS), Malaysia, 2015, DOI: 10.1109/ICITCS.2015.7293017.
- [4].Anthonette D. Cantara and Angie M. Ceniza, “Stress Sensor Prototype:Determining the Stress Level in using a Computer through Validated Self-Made Heart Rate (HR) and Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) Sensors and Fuzzy Logic Algorithm”, International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT), ISSN: 2278-0181, Vol. 5 Issue 03, pp. 28-37,2016.
- [5].Purnendu Shekhar Pandey,” Machine Learning and IoT for Prediction and Detection of Stress”, International Conference on Computational Science and Its Applications (ICCSA), 2017, DOI: 10.1109/ICCSA.2017.8000018.
- [6].Rachmad Setiawan, Fajar Budiman and Wahyu Irfan Basori, “Stress Diagnostic System and Digital Medical Record Based on Internet of Things”, International Seminar on Intelligent Technology and Its Applications (ISITIA), pp. 348-353, Indonesia, 2019, DOI:10.1109/ISITIA.2019.8937273.

[7].Jorge Rodríguez-Arce, Liliana Lara-Flores, Otniel Portillo-Rodríguez and Rigoberto Martínez-Méndez, “Towards an anxiety and stress recognition system for academic environments based on physiological features”, Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine, vol.190, 2020, DOI:10.1016/j.cmpb.2020.105408

IJADST